

Vol:1, Issue: 4 pp: 746-757

JEL Codes:019, 03,019,05

YOUSAFZAI A.U.R (2020). "Indian Anti-satellite Weapon and its Impact on South Asia ",

Vol: 1 Issue: 4 pp: 746-757

Keywords: ASAT Weapon, Pakistan, South Asian, Indian military vision, United States

Article Type Review Article

Indian Anti-satellite Weapon and its Impact on South Asia

Arrived Date
27.08.2020

Accepted Date
02.09.2020

Published Date
31.10.2020

Atif Ur Rahman Yousafzai*

ABSTRACT

The discussion revolves around the value and vulnerability of Satellites as the nations that are in possession of these also possess the means to cause damage to them. Nations preserve supplementary benefit if rummage sale is for the betterment of Humanity instead of making the outer space more militarised. India has developed an ASAT Weapon which ignited multiple factors in the subcontinent which has two nuclear weapon states bound together by geographical contiguity. India is ambitiously vying for a global status by enhancing its military and anti-satellite weapon capabilities to make Pakistan feel insecure. This would usher in an arms race in the South Asian outer space and certainly be detrimental to the deterrence stability. An offensive ASAT capability would increase the cost for an antagonist nation in case of any misfortune, and hence counterbalance the benefits en masse. The Indian military vision of modernisation in advanced technology, especially in space, has motivated, and encouraged its political leadership to take an aggressive position against Pakistan. The view rests on the assumption that attempts to dominate space are bound to backfire, and a war in space between major powers will erupt- a war that cannot be won and must not be fought. In terms of the environmental consequences the spectre of debris-to-debris collisions, hazardous and the chain reaction is the worst form. However, all could be a realistic scenario. The striving of the United States and some other nations, to prevent additional space debris, did formulate mitigation guidelines at the national and international levels. Although these guidelines were appreciated at all facets but could not be applied in letter and spirit.

INTRODUCTION

Discussion about militarization and weaponization of outer space is getting traction. Satellites of space-faring nations have become invaluable for their national security architecture. In the field of strategic studies, the international political system is transforming from unipolarity to the multipolarity. At the same time, they have also become vulnerable to threat of destruction by Anti-Satellites Weapon Systems.

The United States, which had been enjoying the sole super power status, is at the verge of sharing its power with rising China and resurging Russia. Besides Russia and China, India is also striving hard to secure its place in the world power politics with help from the US. Being one of the major space-faring nations, there are tangible indicators that India would not hesitate to join the club of states with space weapons capability. Indian probable space weaponization capability would be detrimental to the deterrence stability in South Asia which houses two nuclear weapons states with border contiguity. Issue of space weaponization in South Asian context needs to be seriously looked into before it is too late.

Outer space is being used for military and strategic purposes. The increasing dependency of militaries on outer space assets for operational and communicational actions creates credible targets for adversaries engaged in war. China and India are the leading South Asian nations who are pursuing

* Research Associate at Research Institute of Development and Evaluation
atifyousafzai334@gmail.com

sophisticated outer space programmes. This gives rise to one of the most unique challenges to the global common of space. Outer space was once the privileged domain of the U.S. and Soviet Union, but now accommodates larger set of countries seeking to enhance their defence capabilities as seen in the anti-satellite weapon tests by China and India respectively.

India has triggered serious concerns when it announced that it also has a strong ASAT capability. P.V Naik critically argued in February 2000 that "Our satellites are vulnerable to ASAT weapon system because our neighbour (China) possesses one." On the other hand Indian demonstration of ASAT test known for "Mission Shakti" which provoked Pakistan to acquire ASAT as well, therefore, technological transformation and varying economic and security scenarios have direct implications for nuclear deterrence and strategic stability between India and Pakistan.

Literature Review

Paper by Carin Zissis on the topic "China's Anti-Satellite Test" thinks that China caused an international uproar on 11 January 2007 when it destroyed one of its own satellites and left hundreds of pieces of dangerous debris in space and led to alarm over the possibility of a space arms race. His observations are valid because after 12 years, India tested its ASAT weapon. A month later, Beijing announced it plans no further similar tests, but the January 2007 test had already established the growing prowess of China's space programme as well as its capability to protect itself from satellite surveillance in the event of war. Despite immediate global demands for an explanation for the test, China waited several days before releasing an official response, prompting questions about its goals. Thus china has started a new arm race in region of south Asia.

Latest study on "Flexing Muscles in Space" The ASAT success by Majumdar and Sayan published in April 2009 where it is discussed about 'Mission Shakti' that how Indian Scientists destroyed a Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellite with an Anti- Satellite (ASAT) missile based on Defence Research & Development Organization (DRDO) Ballistic Missile Defence (BMD) interceptor. Following the successful test, Prime Minister Narendra Modi announced in a televised address to the nation that "India can now defend itself in space, and not just on land, water, and air, after the successes of Mission Shakti." He further stated that the ASAT missile had shot down the Low Earth Orbit satellite within "three minutes of launch", with remarkable precision and technical capability, and India has emerged as the fourth country to have tested such an ASAT weapon after the United States, Russia and China He think that the ASAT weapon chain started from American went to Russia and then came to China and India, and might end at Pakistan's space militarization. According to them, Indian ASAT capability would further make Pakistan dependent on China for acquisition of space technology.

In the paper "Space weapon: A rapidly evolving threat to South Asian Strategic Balance" Saeed Minhas Ahmad has carried out his analysis on ASAT issues in the context of South Asian security who observed that both India and Pakistan mistrust each other; and development of ASAT capability would drive them into another new conflict zone. Pakistan is to be expected its space vision 2047 while India has a exercised space capability programme. If there are no preventive measures, it could prove harmful to peace and deterrence stability in the region. Both states, besides the international community its need to be acquired into account regarding the enhancing situation of space gaining weaponized in South Asian context. Offensive ASAT capability would increase the cost for an antagonist in case of a misfortune, hence counterbalance the benefits en mass. Indian military vision of modernisation in advanced technology, especially in space, has motivated and encouraged its political leaderships to take an aggressive position against Pakistan.

Arvind K. John in "Indian and ASAT Weapon" paper. Has examined the phenomenon of ASAT technology and observed that Indian ASAT capability might raise questions about space debris and political dilemmas. India would have to keep in mind the international and regional influential factors before going for full development of ASAT capability. The Chinese 'double-standards' regarding issues of debris and anti-satellite weapons has posed threats in the region. Pakistan had keen desired an Indian re-think on testing an ASAT weapon, even though it means increased Chinese-Pakistani cooperation on ASAT capability. After the testing of ASAT China it's proven the balance of power of the

region unbalanced in the result India worried and run toward ASAT capacity which might become various arm race in the space technology in South Asian region. While the problem of space debris can be dealt with, as was witnessed in the way the U.S carried out its test in 2008.

1967 Outer Space Treaty, which India and Pakistan are signatories to, prohibits the use of weapons of mass destruction in space but does not restrict the use of conventional weapons. These developments posit adverse affection the strategic equation in South Asia, leading to strategic instability, and can undermine nuclear deterrence and bring about a South Asian arms race in space. Security dilemma in South Asia has prompted defensive and offensive reactions from rival states in the region, exacerbating repercussions on the South Asian strategic landscape. Analysis of the issues suggests that keeping space free from weaponization can alleviate strategic instability in South Asia.

Research Methodology

My research uses a combination of descriptive and analytical research designs. I describe in a logical manner as to what are the Indian anti-satellite capabilities, then I employ analytical method to evaluate how they impact strategic stability. Combining both methods leads me to described, in a logical and coherent manner the anti-satellite capabilities of India. Such a research methodology consists of both types of quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection and measurement. The sources contain primary and secondary data-bases and involve questionnaires, expert interviews, archives, digital library sources, books, research articles, journals, newspapers and websites. Some data has been collected from the various sources of Indian side as well, which was critically analysed using quantitative techniques for analysis and measurement of variables. Qualitative content analysis was used to gather meaning form the qualitative data. This method included identifying patterns inside the data collected, categorizing them into themes, and then linking these themes to the theoretical framework established for the study.

Significance of Research

The significance of this research is that it addresses a current topic which is crucial to the security of Pakistan. Therefore, this research explains the nature of anti-satellite weapons, technological transformation occurring in space, varying economic and security scenarios that have direct implications for deterrence and strategic stability between India and Pakistan. The research is likely to contribute to the strategic stability debate; and draw attention of researchers, policy makers and strategic thinkers, who might get some ideas about the emerging threats due to weaponization of space and attendant national security issues and security dilemmas. The students of IR, Strategic Studies and the educated citizens would find this research useful in recognizing the importance of space and its security connotations for Pakistan.

The Research would significantly highlight India's ASAT test and the vanity of international regimes prevailing the activities of outer space and failure to formulate obligatory rules to regulate countries' space actions. Furthermore, the absence of 'no rules' opens a window for states to exploit these legal loopholes for their geopolitical and geostrategic considerations, while threatening the global prosperity on the one hand and setting an instance for other states to follow ensemble on the other. Unchecked 'weaponization of outer space' and 'prestige'-led space arms race has the potential to trigger dangerous 'cascading effects' for international peace and stability.

Historical background of ASAT Technology

The space programme began in the 1950s, when the Soviet Union took the initiative to launch a satellite with the name of Sputnik 1 which demonstrated its capability on 4 October, 1957, after a few months later the U.S launch of Explorer 1 on 1 January, 1958. This paved the way for experts and scientist to discover further ideas for productive utilization of space technology, while many ideas were perused that, it could be use strongly for military objectives, as well the most success of it to gather information and use it for spying purposes. In the beginning, the first class information system was designed to gather information for weather purposes, which called weather satellite, that image and monitoring the earth in various spectral bands to determine cloud cover, moisture content, and relevant information. The second class information has included various function such as, voice, data

and image information, which has numerous commercial system specially dedicated for military system.

The Anti-Satellite Weapons

ASAT technology is an instrument which is considered as a capable of destroying or disabling space assets for reasons such as military or civilian, offensive or defensive. The ASAT technology is further divided into two categories: kinetic and non-kinetic. Kinetic ASAT is specially used for physical strike in order to destroy the object, such as ballistic missiles, drones in order to pull down an object out of orbit or hit the explosion in proximity to the object or any item can be targeted to black and damage the target satellite and their movement. In addition it could be used for further space assets for instance a communication satellite could be used for the destruction of any physical space objects. A non-kinetic ASAT technology used for the various non-physical means for the destruction and disability of any space objects, the non-kinetic ASAT has the capability to target the frequency jamming, blinding lasers or cyber-attack.

Satellite jamming: It has the ability to create any contradiction, when it takes place between a satellite and users on the ground particularly occur with radio communication, and it can be attempted with either uplink or downlink in both cases, such as toward satellite and or ground. The attacker might be interfering with the reception of satellite signals by earthly devices in case of downlink would not actually do anything with satellite.

Manoeuvring satellites: The manoeuvring satellite has the function and ability to hit the targeted satellites in the absence of certain cooperation, which might be base for ASAT weapon as well, where it is capable of damaging the satellite as it could be temporary or permanent, where different type of method would be applicable to adopt preventive measure of debris. The are several nations and organizations, such as Russia, Japan, China and European Space Agency that have the autonomous rendezvous and close propinquity capability at various stages which have been developed this.

Ground-based laser: Ground-based lasers has been designed to interfere with satellite sensors or damage a satellites body, in addition, the low-powered lasers can be used to dazzle the sensors of high-resolution inspection satellite are the inhibiting observation of the region which are kilometres in size. In the contrast a high-powered laser has the capacity, to partially blind the satellite by damaging relatively a small section of sensor or can bed damage the structure of satellite trained on a satellite sensor.

Dr Raja Qaiser, said in an interview that anti-satellite weapon is something which is being used by the major part was established for in space. It is believed to have used a spin-off technology from Indian ABM system, and India's files to develop a multi-layer than multi-phased missile defense system and they can deter and dissuade the adversary. This is what their entire mission Shakti had been for and this is something which India and Indian State craft has deeply politicized as well. Just three days before the elections of 2019; Modi made a speech on the national television, and he announced that India had acquired ASAT technology basically he was trying to project India as a major hegemonic power. By this speech and by this achievement he was trying to convince his message that he has equated India with other major powers.

The Type of Technology used by India

India carried out an ASAT test on 27 March, 2019, when it destroyed one of its own satellites in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) at 300 km above the Earth. India became the 4th country after the USA, Russia and China to develop a proven ASAT Capability. Prithvi Defence Vehicle (PDV Mark-II), which is an Anti Ballistic Missile Interceptor Missile was used to, was used as Hit-to-Kill capable Kinetic Kill vehicle, the modified version was the part of ongoing ballistic missile defence programme. The missile technology was employed in order to achieve the target by striking and shattering the targeted satellite which contain, "Kinetic Kill Vehicle or Hit to Kill" in most of the missile, the metal warhead is utilized in order to break the target satellite with the support of high velocity and impact energy. India's ASAT test also undoubtedly validated several emerging Indian ballistic missile defence technologies, including the

imaging infrared sensor in the PDV MK-II's kill vehicle and its divert and position control system, but the larger gains sought were strategic.

According to their department of DRDO that PDV-MK II as completely new missile technology has been developed particularly for ASAT purpose, where some technologies of the BMD interceptors also have been utilized, and there were many new technologies included which were part of the first kinetic kill weapon. The missile has three-stage interceptor with two solid propellant rocket motor stages weighing approximately 18 tones as well with the height of 13 metres and having capability "hit to kill" as kill vehicle (KV), which was used under the Mission Shakti, which targeted the satellite. The first stage of the missile has the capacity to separate at 45 km after lift-off, on the other hand the second stage has the potential to separate at 110 km. The 3rd stage of the missile will travel to in the range of 200 km to destroy the targeted satellite. The onboard advanced terminal guidance system, which featured a strap-down non gimbaled Imaging Infrared (IIR) seeker as well as an inertial navigation system used a Ring Laser Gyroscope (RLGs) to identify and track the satellite orbiting in LEO. The desired altitude and velocity two rocket engine stages have been used, from the front of nose IIR seeker located within that in order to lock onto the target satellite and guide it towards at a closing speed of almost 10 km.

PDV Mark-II has two-stage solid propellant rocket motors with advanced Thrust Vectoring Control (TVC), on-board Imaging Infrared (IIR), and Ring Laser Gyroscope (RLG) inertial navigation systems for accurate tracking and hitting the target satellite. PDV Mark II hit the target with accuracy less than 10 cm. The Thrust Vector Control (TVC) system has been used for the correction in case of trajectory of the missile, which contain larger thrusters at the top of missiles while cylindrical body at roughly its Center of Gravity (CG) including small thrusters inserted into near rear of the missiles. The BMD systems designed by the DRDO which links connected to the Radar and data communication to DRDO, which were deployed across a wide ground span, where it has the capability to track the entire satellite interception effectively by the ASAT missile. Significance of Indian ASAT Test: i) It gives India the capability to degrade and destroy communication, reconnaissance and intelligence gathering capabilities of countries by destroying their space-based assets. ii) It confirms that India has the capability to intercept intercontinental ballistic missiles, and its BMD system is effective. iii) It enables India to claim the right to be involved in formation of future international norms and guidelines with regards to militarisation of outer space.

Rizwan Zeb, Phd scholar, expressed his view that, the Indian ASAT test involved a ballistic missile defence interceptor, the Prithvi Delivery Vehicle Mark-II (PDV MK-II) that struck and destroyed an Indian Microsat-R satellite. Dr Muhammad Munir, PhD scholar says that, India used Ballistic Missile Defence Interceptor Technology known as the Prithvi Delivery Vehicle Mark-II (PDV MK-II). India's Defence Research and Development Organization (DRDO) played a critical role in developing this system.

Indian ASAT created Space debris

The most important factor regarding the ASAT technology during its creation was the issue of space debris which is the biggest threat to the satellite due the huge amount of space growing debris. In the current time there are approximately 22,000 items, larger than 10 cm size, in space an around 500,000 objects ranging between 1 to 10 cm, while more than 20,000 space debris pieces have been created by the Chinese and U.S ASAT weapon demonstration.

In the result of Indian ASAT test has been conducted at an altitude of about 300 km, where it has created huge amount of debris which is expected to be extended beyond the original parent object orbit, where some fragments spread as well climbed into the upper low-earth orbit, where it would be definitely dangerous for the other satellites. On May 1, the Dutch satellite tracker mentioned regarding the Indian mission, "It was conducted in a less responsible way than originally claimed." As in explanation, he stated that the demonstration of Indian ASAT has created huge debris with much longer orbital lifetime's in some cases up to 10 times longer.

The Indian ASAT impact on South Asian strategic stability

There is much difference between the South Asian and Cold War context of strategic and deterrence stability due to some key determinants of stability in the South Asian region, however, the developments of Indian in defence-related technology and weapons such as BMD, ASAT and outer space-based enhancement has negatively affected the regional stability and its deterrence. The technological advancement in the field of defence and increasing capacity and the identification of enemy and its target will create desire to first strike by India, which ultimately to force Pakistan to undertake the way to defend the territory as well as expand its nuclear arsenal.

The Indian conventional behaviour and desire for the hegemonic status over Pakistan and the South Asian Region is increasing with the various dynamics, where recently the major concern is the development of space asset, where India conventional deterrence against its adversaries. The deterrence stability and escalation can be ensured in the form of where both rivals' forces in the same position of security and balanced defence lines, while no one has any extraordinary powerful weapon to surpass their capability and dare to attack each other.

The South Asian region is centre of attention for all major powers as well for the international community particularly for the United States in the past, and will remaining so in the future. The importance of the South Asian region reflects in the behaviour of the world powers and the United States foreign security policy calculus basically due to the great strategic, political, an economic significant as well other powers of the world which have strong interest association with the region. The convergence of geostrategic interest in the region, which presently designed by India and the United States in order to lead a realignment of its strategic relations. There are several unstable factors which lead the conflict between United States and Pakistan in the region, such as the presence of the U.S. in the region and its ally's forces in Afghanistan for fighting terrorism. On the other hand the United State trying to pursue its interest as its rebalancing policy in the region in order to contains the rise of China, where India has strong ties with the U.S. and playing an instrumental role in helping the United States to Influence and achieves its strategic interests in the region. The region itself became a victim of the contradiction due the confusing role of the players like China tries to balance its relation with the United States, while it would turn its impact negatively on relation with India, which ultimately discard relations with Pakistan. Therefore action-reaction attitude caused a ripple effect in the bilateral relations between China-India, India-Pakistan, and China-United States.

There are multi-factors behind the stabilizing and destabilizing position of the region where the adversarial relations between states affect at various facet, hence the leading factor one them would be full-pledge utilization of military uses as well political leadership. If the capabilities create an environment which pave way for the war fighting or creates temptation for war waging that would be worse kind of incentives, which lead to destabilizing the region. On the other hand, if there is certain technology which gains by a state aimed to provides general intelligence gathering and use for verification for an arms control arrangements would be stabilizing factors. In the context of South Asia there has does not exist any certain category of space-based capabilities, whether it's on bilateral or multilateral level which control arms and verified arrangement procedure through space-based assets. In addition in the case of satellite whether it's military or civilian while the distinction between them is in a gray area, even most of the space assets are uses for a dual purpose. In the South Asian region Indian space build-up is kind of severe threat alarming the strategic balance of the region, while remaining to vast disparities with Pakistan especially in space-based capabilities.

Strategic analysts such as Dr Muhammad Munir believe that, ASAT would affect the Deterrence Stability in the region, the cornerstone of Pakistan's delivery system for nuclear weapons is its ballistic and cruise missile capabilities. Such as tested technology base in the form of ASAT would provide India the capability in targeting the incoming offensive ballistic missiles. Thus, the Indian ASAT capability would enhance its BMD system that may undermine Pakistan's deterrence capability through its ballistic missiles. Obviously it would have severe implications for the deterrence stability in the region. The indicators of the resultant deterrence instability due to Indian ASAT capabilities include: possibility of doctrinal shift from 'No First Use' (NFU) to 'First Use' about which there has

been a serious debate going on; may make India overconfidence having the option of launching surgical strikes under a nuclear strategy against alleged terrorist camps inside Pakistan. Indian aggressive policies would further make it dismissive about reinitiating composite dialogue with Pakistan; such capability would enhance Indian efforts for permanent membership of the UNSC; Indian offensive capability may affect Pakistan's Space Vision-2047 programme.

Dr Raja Qaiser, has said that, indeed, it would trigger more defence spending it would you know to more ambitious space programmes it would lead to you know in South Asia. It would lead to an unnecessary arms race. This satellite have always had dual used they can be used for communication purposes and can we use violence for reconcile.

Space Arms Race in South Asia and weakening of deterrence and strategic stability

Outer space is an emerging hub for the weaponization and international and regional politics, where arms race is being triggered by various factors in the outer space, which is on higher side of trajectory. On the other hand the arms controllers are much worried regarding the increasing competition in the space, where each nation tries to pursue their capability, while several of them tested the ASAT capability, which is generally kept covert at many levels which would bring a severe result in the region in term of arm race particularly between the rivalry powers. In the South Asian context India has an offensive mode of space capability in various areas whether its outer space and terrestrial or space, definitely it would become a drastic threat for the adversary such as misadventure. Indian rapid advancement in the space technology as well motivating its political leadership to take an aggressive action against its enemies, while the adversaries get triggered to take competitive action in the region.

The establishment of the Space Cell within the Integrated Defence Headquarters was considered as a first step toward space development program, which has been taken more than decade ago. In addition the government of India has formed as an interim institutional arrangement with name a Defence Space Agency (DSA), while the imitative has been taken more recently as a considered a first step toward a full-fledged Aerospace set up. The DSA was basically designed for the space-security related policy and strategy while the government is establishing a Defence Space Research Organization (DSRO) akin to DRDO for the purpose to conduct research work and development activities for various types of capability while need for the strategies set out by the DSA. Along with these all set ups, and institutional arrangements which required much integration and space conventional military operations with changing nature of the warfare as well a greater reliance on space based command and other space related activities.

Indian ASAT Test Impact on Environment

Since the emerging of the concept regarding the space technology all relevant states agree upon the restriction of ASAT development and their testing, while in that case many questions are raised that how should to be limited or comprehensive such as test-ban and structure. In the beginning among the major ASAT holder nations drafted a simple proposal which contain that, to bar tests in space of any ASAT system, where it creates a huge amount of debris which would have a long-lasting affect in the environment due to the spread of debris. On the other hand all space activities at least preclude or controllable, however, it may has the result in some debris and accidents the pollution as the disastrous Chinese 2007 event, which spawned an unprecedented cluster of enduring hazardous material, while rest of the space activities might be normal and dispersal of debris or might be unaffected.

Dr Ahmad Ishaq's, perspective regarding this is that, primarily ASAT weapons rendered from isotropic nuclear weapon to electronic means, primarily a nuclear weapon deteriorated in space is also an ASAT weapon because one it is deteriorated. Consequently, it will leave a massive electromagnetic pulse in street and it would fly the electronic system of all the satellite a nuclear weapon is potentially ASAT weapon. However, it is banned under outer space treaty, conventional weapon is not banned under the Outer space Treaty. If Outer Space Treaty include the deteriorated of conventional weaponry space then it will denuclearize the world, primarily because the outer space treaty will restrict the transportation of nuclear weapons in space. Therefore, every ballistic missile defence bill passed

through space so if a outer space treaty is accepted in its letter and spirit then it will ban the transportation of nuclear weapons, in space. If a weapon carrying a nuclear weapon is banned in the outer space then there are only cruel missile left and there will be no shot run ballistic missile. The outer space treaty is not implemented in letter and spirits because it does not restricts the transportation of nuclear weapon in or within space likewise, the conventional weapons are not banned under the outer space treaty. Therefore primarily ASAT weapon is a recipe for security dilemma and arms race in outer space between India and Pakistan, India and China and the United State, there are a lot of security values.

Conclusion

India is ambitious to acquire global and regional hegemonic status and is struggling hard for it, through projecting its military strength. Progress and development in anti-satellite weapons, ballistic missile defence, and surveillance and intelligence capabilities are a major concern for Pakistan. India's anti-satellite weapons capability is making Pakistan feel insecure and usher in an arms race between India and Pakistan in the outer space. Indian ASAT capability is an offensive capability which induces fear and security dilemma for Pakistan. The strategic stability of South Asia is in question and there is need to scrutinize the changing dilemma of security in the region. Pakistan needs to pursue its own ASAT capability without overstressing its economic resources. India is the fourth country, which gained the ASAT capability after the U.S., Russia and China, the demonstration of Indian ASAT weapon.

On 27 March, 2019, India tested an ASAT weapon with the code name 'Mission Shakti', where the satellite was targeted from among the India's existing satellite Microsat-R orbiting in Lower Earth Orbit (LEO) at the height of km 284. The Prithvi Defence Vehicle Mark II (PDV-MK II) missile has been utilized as a modified version of DRDO's PDV anti-ballistic interceptor missile; the modified version was the part of ongoing ballistic missile defense programme.

As a result of the Indian ASAT test which has been conducted at an altitude of about 300 km, where it has created huge amount of debris, which is expected to be extended beyond the original parent object orbit, where some fragments spread as well climbed into the upper low-earth orbit, where it would be definitely dangerous for other satellites. The USA and Russia have developed their ASAT capabilities with their own justifications as dedicated their systems and claimed for different objectives. The U.S. perceived threat of Soviet orbital bombardment system, in order to build up weapon into orbit and to be able to defend their space from the enemy, as pursued ABM/ASAT system. China has become a capable possessor of its own homing vehicle and has destroyed its aging weather satellite by using a mobile ground-based missile, which was took place in January 2007. Therefore this harsh ASAT demonstration produced more firm debris than any previous incident in space, which caused a great deal of international concern. Since the 1980s China had been working on this technology which is known for "Hit to Kill" as well on both weapons, such as ASAT weapon and ballistic missile defence, which is father paved way for ballistic missile defence test in January 2010.

The Indian aggressive advancement toward space militarization is a big threat for Pakistan as well for the South Asian region, where China has a large space programme in the orbit. Indian expansion in outer space gives it space-based reconnaissance, surveillance and communication capabilities which contribute the destabilizing component to the military, nuclear and strategic balance in South Asia. The development of the Indian ASAT programme which essentially is weaponization of space as well, would trigger the antagonized relations between two nuclear powers, which affect the security of Pakistan as well the strategic stability of South Asia. Several great powers expressed their deep concern toward the militarization of space indeed it's not in the interest of any country, while Indian ASAT weapons seems clearly a threat warning for Pakistan's security. As India wants to emerge as major global power by increasing her military and strategic capabilities, especially, in space; Pakistan should seek Chinese cooperation to balance India.

The striving of the U.S. including other nations have taken action to prevent additional space debris, which presented in the form of guidelines and mitigation at various level national and international and were appreciated at all facet but unfortunately could not be applied in spirit. All states agrees that

it would have deep negative impact on peace as well the environment region as well a severe threat of outer space militarization. Indian itself one of them warned that “China’s ASAT test is definitely a concern for all countries with satellite launch capabilities” as well highlighted the space debris issues. Indian demonstration of ASAT weapon has proven that, despite these all statements and steps which openly violating the international norms and laws. Even India has not generally asserted the belief that ASAT testing or use is already a violation of the world community's expectation.

Recommendations

In order to make the way for enhanced strategic stability in South Asia, this study presents the following recommendations:

- Pakistan should create ‘Defence Space Agency’ to develop capabilities required to protect its interests in outer space and deal with threat of space war.
- Pakistan should develop its own ASAT capabilities to counter Indian ISR capabilities and to instil fear of retaliation if India thinks of blinding Pakistan in future war.
- Technical capabilities and Research & Development to develop ASAT weapons would also help Pakistan acquire many capabilities including ability to develop advanced ICBMs and delivery vehicles for satellite launches. So Pakistan should pursue ASAT capability.
- Pakistan should increase its cooperation with China in developing satellites and ASAT capability.
- Pakistan should whole-heartedly support Russia-China joint proposal of “Treaty Against Weaponization of Space.”
- Pakistan should actively support international normative regimes and movements against space debris and to create pressure against development of ASAT weapons.
- Pakistan should promote the idea of space being the Global Common, and must work with international community so that the domain of space is used by the whole humanity for peaceful purposes.

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